

Scottish peat values and ecosystem services: Prioritising the gaps

Workshop report

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Executive Summary

Peatlands are an iconic Scottish landscape which provide a wide range of ecosystem services, from internationally valuable carbon storage to locally vital energy provision and livestock grazing. To ensure long-term sustainable management we must consider the value of the non-carbon services provided by peatland, how these are impacted by management for carbon, and how services could be enhanced alongside carbon management, or damage mitigated. In this report we analyse the outcomes from two workshops with stakeholders involved in the policy development, and implementation of peatland management to address the following objectives:

1. Validate evidence map of ecosystem service values from peatland (Roberts et al., 2023), including:
 - a. Identifying any ecosystem services missing from the evidence map
 - b. Adding any valuation not found through the literature
2. Connect evidence map to peatland management in practice, including:
 - a. Identifying any site, or region, specific variation
 - b. Detailing thresholds for ecosystem services provision (e.g., minimum water quality)
 - c. Recognising bundles of ecosystem services
3. Prioritise valuation gaps with most importance for management.

Key results

- Twenty-two new services were identified, as well as additional sources of data for timber, water quality, and energy.
- The Borders, Central Belt and Cairngorms National Park were identified as areas with high service provision.
- Thresholds for services produced from peatlands were challenging to identify, and likely to vary by site.
- Three distinct bundles of ecosystem services became apparent, being linked specifically to carbon, non-extractive use (e.g., recreation) and traditional use (e.g., fuel). These are not exclusive of each other, but represent three distinct use types.

- Water quality was identified as the most important gap in economic valuation of peatland ecosystem services, followed by flooding, energy, timber, and carbon storage.

Next steps

This work forms part of the CentrePeat project (2022-2027), within the Scottish Government Strategic Research Program. The results will feed into developing a toolkit for valuing the most important peatland ecosystem services. Using choice experiments we will investigate the trade-offs between competing services, and potential options for mitigating this competition. The toolkit will later be applied to case studies.

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Introduction

Peatlands are an iconic Scottish landscape, which provide a wide range of ecosystem services, from internationally valuable carbon storage to locally vital energy provision and livestock grazing (Roberts et al., 2023). Peat soils are a key part of Scotland's drive for net zero, Scotland's natural capital accounts estimate that Scottish peatlands store approximately 3 billion tonnes of carbon (Scottish Government, 2022). However, although healthy peatlands are carbon stores, the majority of Scotland's peatlands are net carbon emitters and in poor ecological condition (Artz et al., 2019; Evans et al., 2017), though these emissions do show a declining trend (Brown et al., 2023). Managing peatlands to safeguard their remaining carbon store and reduce contemporary net carbon emissions is therefore a key goal of the Scottish Government, as well as the use of peatland restoration to support nature-based solutions and improvement of biodiversity outcomes. This work is supported by a pledge of over £250 million for peatland restoration between 2020 and 2030 (Forbes, 2020).

A key component of the management of peatland for carbon is its ability to persist over millennial timescales. For this long-term sustainability to be realised, understanding of the value of the wide range of additional services which peatlands provide is vital. Although the value of peatlands for carbon is the best understood service (Roberts et al., 2023), other services with consistent economic valuation include burning for energy (Cannell et al., 1999; Dickie et al., 2019), extraction of growing media (Scottish Government, 2022), food production including grazing (Artz et al., 2014), and wildlife watching (Glenk and Martin-Ortega, 2018). Services which are known to be produced, but not yet valued, include cultural heritage (Game and Wildlife Conservation Trust, 2015), historical preservation (RSPB, n.d.), water quality (Glenk et al., 2021a; Glenk and Martin-Ortega, 2018), game hunting, including both deer stalking and grouse shooting (Ludwig et al., 2018), water flow regulation (Allott et al., 2019) and disease control (Gilbert, 2013; Roberts et al., 2023). To ensure long-term sustainable management which benefits carbon storage we must therefore also consider the value of the non-carbon services provided by peatland. Accounting for these services in management will enable strategies to be chosen which maximise local benefits, and highlight where trade-offs or compensation may be needed for services which are not compatible with management for carbon.

In the first year of the CentrePeat project we carried out a literature review to identify the existing understanding of wider peatland values in the published literature (Roberts et al., 2023). In this report we analyse the outcome from two workshops with stakeholders involved in the policy development, and implementation of peatland management to address the following objectives:

1. Validate evidence map of ecosystem service values from peatland (Roberts et al., 2023), including:
 - a. Identifying any ecosystem services missing from the evidence map
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2. Connect evidence map to peatland management in practice, including:
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 - b. Detailing thresholds for ecosystem services provision (e.g., minimum water quality)
 - c. Recognising bundles of ecosystem services
3. Prioritise valuation gaps with most importance for management.

The results from this project will guide the development of a "Peatland Valuation Framework" completed in 2027.

Methods

Workshops

We carried out two workshops in September 2023, one in Edinburgh and one online, with individuals and organisations connected to peatlands in Scotland. Stakeholders were selected to cover users of the full range of services provided by peatlands, intending to get a balance of stakeholders in each workshop (Table 1).

Table 1 Stakeholder types included in workshops and interviews.

Stakeholder type	Reason for invite
Local community leaders, with connection to peatlands	People living near peatlands may depend on them for livelihoods, hold cultural values, and be most impacted by management decisions, including on cutting peat for fuel. However, the link to peatland may not be obvious to individual residents, and so leaders with particular knowledge of peatland will be sought.
Government agencies	Responsible for peatland policy, with knowledge of the existing governance structure, challenges, and interlinkages with other environmental areas.
Agriculture and forestry	Direct experience of managing peatlands, including both extraction and restoration.
Peatland (environmental) conservation organisations	Familiar with challenges and values related to peatland and the impact on environment. Linked to biodiversity related services.
Game hunting	Carry out recreational activities on areas which include peatlands. This includes both deer stalking and grouse shooting.
Tourism	Recreational activities related to peatland, including iconic landscapes and walking routes. Tourist leaders with particular connections to peatlands, rather than general tourism, will be targeted.
Whisky producers	Peat is a key component of Scottish whisky production, and often part of the selling point for distilleries, either explicitly or in images used in advertising.
Water regulators or companies	Peatland has large impacts on water quality and quantity.
Wind farms	Optimal sites for windfarms often coincide with peatland sites, leading to a trade-off in energy production and peatland protection.

Workshops ran for a total of 4 hours, and the in-person and online workshop followed the same agenda. Following a brief introduction to the project, participants took part in four structured activities:

Identifying missing ecosystem services and data – As a whole group participants viewed a table of the ecosystem services as identified through the literature review (Table 2) and added any services they felt were missing. They also shared any sources of valuation data that they were aware of, moving some existing services into higher classifications of knowledge with this additional data. In the online workshop this was carried out via Miro.

Table 2 Strength of evidence of ecosystem service values from peatlands from Roberts et al. 2023.

High strength of evidence	Mid strength of evidence	Low strength of evidence
Carbon storage	Energy	Timber
	Growing media	Water quality
	Food production	Disease control
	Wildlife watching	Educational services
		Game hunting
		Cultural heritage
		Historical preservation

In analysis, the new services across both workshops were combined. Where a service was placed into different categories in each workshop the higher level was retained. Additional data signposted was located and its suitability for use in peatland ecosystem services valuation assessed.

Site or region specific variation – Participants were split into two groups and provided maps of Scotland. Using markers (in person) or Miro tools (online) participants identified the geographical areas where the peatland services they were familiar with were produced.

The resulting four maps from the two groups in the in-person and online workshops were merged into a combined map, with services assumed to be present if they occurred in a location on any one single map. Polygons were drawn in QGIS to approximate the location drawn on the paper, or Miro, map.

Thresholds for ecosystem services – In a carousel exercise with three stations participants identified thresholds for services either over which they would no longer consider management needed, or under which management for that services would not be feasible to carry out. This was carried out in three groups in person, and two groups using a Miro board online. These were summarised directly from the information provided by participants.

Bundles of ecosystem services - Participants were grouped into those with similar interests and asked to link services that may alter together with positive (an increase in one service would lead to an increase in another) or negative (an increase in one service would lead to a decrease in another) links, to create a conceptual map of peatland ecosystem services. This was carried out on a Miro board for the online workshop.

The conceptual maps from each workshop were converted to matrices using mental modeler (<https://dev.mentalmodeler.com>), an online software. Each link was represented by a 1 (positive), 0 (no link) or -1 (negative). The links in each matrix were compared. Where links agreed, or a link appeared in one map but not all, these links were taken forward into the final model. Where links between services disagreed discussions were had between the project team to decide on which link to use. These can be seen in Appendix 1.

This final matrix was then analysed with FCMapper in R (R Core Team, 2022; Turney and Bachhofer, 2016) to identify the services with the higher number of links to other services. These central services were used to identify bundles of ecosystem services which could be managed together and highlight trade-offs.

Valuation gaps - Finally, participants voted for the valuation gaps that would be most useful for them to have data on. In the in person workshop each person was given three stickers and asked place these next to the services that they felt they needed more valuation data. In this workshop multiple stickers could be placed on one service, or the stickers could be placed on different services depending on the preferences of the participant. Due to limitations of the online voting software participants in the online workshop could only place one vote for each service but were also given a total of three votes.

Votes from both workshops were counted to identify the highest priority valuation gaps in peatland ecosystem services. Discussions from workshops were used to contextualise these gaps.

We also conducted one interview, with questions designed to follow the workshop structure. Results from the interview will be integrated throughout the report.

Results

General

A total of 16 participants were involved across both workshops (Table 3), with nine attending in person and seven attending online. Participants included a range of stakeholder types, but did not include representatives from game hunting, tourism (although organisations involved had some knowledge of tourism through their work) or wind farms. Although a separate conversation was had with one wind farm company, they did not provide any data.

Table 3 Stakeholders involved in workshops

Stakeholder type	Organisations represented
Local community leaders, with connection to peatlands	Shetland Amenity
Government agencies	Scottish Government, ClimateXChange, UKCEH
Agriculture and forestry	Scottish Forestry, Forestry and Land Scotland
Peatland (environmental) conservation organisations	NatureScot, Peatland Action, The Flow Country Partnership, National Trust for Scotland
Game hunting	None
Whisky producers	Scottish Whisky Association
Water supplier	Scottish Water
Wind farms	None

Validate evidence map of ecosystem service values

Based on findings from the literature review (Roberts et al., 2023) we presented twelve potential services produced from peatlands. Workshop participants added an additional twenty-two services not identified in the academic literature, and identified additional sources of data for timber, water quality and energy (Table 4).

Table 4 Ecosystem services provided by peatlands and their strength of evidence for their value. Services in bold were added during the workshop, and services in italics were identified via the literature review, but had additional valuation information provided by the workshop participants.

High strength of evidence	Medium strength of evidence	Low strength of evidence
Carbon Storage	Recreation	Biodiversity Credits
<i>Timber</i>	Growing Media	Disease Control
Financial Returns (Carbon credits)	Food	Educational Services
Flooding prevention	Game	Historical Preservation
<i>Water Quality</i>	Wildlife Watching	Cultural Heritage
Jobs in Rural Areas	Recreational Environment of Biodiversity	Regulation of Water Scarcity
Surface Cooling (Albedo)	Scientific Interest	Mitigation of Fire Risk
<i>Energy</i>	Wellbeing	Fish Farming
	Agriculture/ Grazing	Military Training Grounds
	Whisky Industry	Commercial Use for Recreation
	Air Quality	Filter Toxic Chemicals
	Archaeology/Paleoenvironments research	Wildfire Mitigation
	Building	

Additional evidence signposted

Timber

Workshop participants identified a report funded by ClimateXChange which estimated the area of coniferous plantation on Scottish deep peat and peaty soils as 5,797km² (Vanguelova et al., 2018). Data from Forest research reports a 2023 timber price of £30.33/m³ (Braby, 2023). To complete the estimation of value yield estimates, such as those used in modelling of carbon capture potential of alternative forestry scenarios (Matthews et al., 2020) would need to be carried out accounting for productive species on peat soils in particular. Although this only represents one study, given the scale of the data it would be considered high strength of evidence.

Financial returns

Financial returns in this case referred to the value of carbon offsetting through management of peatlands to maximise carbon storage. The Peatland Carbon Code provides a mechanism for the sale of carbon credits, with a 2022 average price of £23.95 (IUCN Peatland Programme, 2023). Estimating the financial returns of peatland carbon will require long term study of the costs of restoration and maintenance of healthy peatland, building on existing work from the Peatland Action program (Glenk et al., 2021b).

Flood prevention

Impacts of peatland management techniques on natural flood management have been studied in the UK with potential applications to Scotland. Researchers at the University of Manchester have identified that revegetation, including sphagnum planting, and gully and drain blocking reduce peak flows at small scales, with modelled reductions at larger spatial scales (Allott et al., 2019). The costs of flood events has been estimated in previous research at £56,776 - £76,035 per property based on insurance costs (Owusu et al., 2015; Werritty, 2007). Estimating the value of natural flood

management from peatlands would therefore require further modelling of impacts on number of properties protected from flooding.

Water quality

Workshop participants identified potential sources of data from Scottish Water and SEPA in estimating the costs of water cleaned. Previous work on the costs of soil erosion estimated costs to drinking water treatment at £22.4m annually (Rickson et al., 2020), however, this work relied on costs data from 1990-1997, which will need updating. Further work will also be needed to differentiate the impacts of peatlands in particular in improving water quality, as opposed to other soil types.

Jobs in rural areas

Although no immediate data was identified by the workshop participants, they did recognise that peatland management for carbon or biodiversity in particular provides employment that may be comparable to timber, which is often the alternative land use in these areas. A project estimating this and funded by ClimateXChange is expected in March 2024.

Surface cooling

The dark colour of exposed peat was highlighted as being an important contributor to increases in surface temperature when compared to vegetated peat. Only one specific peatland study was identified (Worrall et al., 2019), however the relative reflectivity of different surfaces is well documented, so application to peatlands was anticipated to be straightforward.

Energy

Although no representatives from windfarms were present, the potential energy gain from windfarms placed on peat was identified by workshop participants as possible to estimate based on number of windfarm sites and projected energy production. It is likely that this is commercially sensitive data, however a report from ClimateXChange will be available in summer of 2024.

Workshop participants highlighted that splitting of energy into two distinct services, as fuel for burning and as a site for windfarms, which has been taken forward into the remaining analysis.

[Connect evidence map to peatland management in practice](#)

Site or region specific variation

Fourteen services were mapped by workshop participants, ranging from widely distributed services such as recreation, tourism, timber, and flood control, to highly specific locations of extraction for growing media and whisky. Participants also identified the proposed Sutherland spaceport as another potential service, however this has a very small footprint and is unlikely to be a widespread need for peatland across Scotland (Figure 1). It should be noted when using this map that it is only illustrative of the perceptions of delivery and use of services from the point of view of participants and should therefore be used in conjunction with local surveys if guiding management.

Existing Ecosystem Services in Scotland in Peatlands

Figure 1 Existing ES in Scotland peatland areas. Source: produced by authors using information provided through workshops. Source: Map made by authors using information provided during four workshops, also, two extra layers were used: Ordnance Survey Map of Scotland. The peat map data was developed in the following published work: Aitkenhead, M.J., Coull, M.C., 2019. Mapping soil profile depth, bulk density and carbon stock in Scotland using remote sensing and spatial covariates. *European Journal of Soil Science*. 10.1111/ejss.12916. The GIS data layer is available on the Hutton Open Science portal at <https://openscience.hutton.ac.uk>.

The map of ecosystem services highlights some areas as potential sites of conflict in peatland management for service provision. These areas are centred around the more populated or tourist areas of Scotland: the Borders, Central Belt, and Cairngorms National Park. The multiple uses of these areas is not surprising, they are accessible to the highest number of services users. Management in these areas therefore needs to carefully consider trade-offs between services, particularly those such as flood control, that are not spatially interchangeable.

Maintaining the distribution of services is also an important consideration in peatland management. For services such as flood control, interchangeability between sites of production is not possible, i.e., flood control is needed for each location. Alternatively, extraction for growing media feeds a national or international market distant from its production. In this case the availability of alternative sites can provide a viable alternative. This is a particularly relevant consideration for management for carbon, not presented on the map as all peatlands store carbon (although the condition of many means they are currently carbon sources). Although highly valuable, the storage of carbon is a global benefit and a public good. That is, carbon storage alone does not give higher benefit to those spatially close to the peatland, and they are more often the ones bearing the cost. The map produced by participants provides a broad consideration of the local services that may need to be considered in peatland management. This could be through either choosing management options which maximise the production of all desired services, providing alternative provision of services (e.g., through built infrastructure to reduce flooding), or compensation where appropriate. For specific peatland management projects work with local stakeholders would also be required to understand the most appropriate method for mitigating these trade-offs.

Not all of the services mapped were as well agreed upon by all workshop participants. Whisky was identified as being a use of peat in Moray due to the presence of distilleries. Although Speyside whisky is more traditionally non-peated, some lightly peated whiskys are produced here. Windfarms were not unanimously accepted as a service by all participants, given that they represent pieces of infrastructure produced by humans. Instead, a more specific way of seeing this as a service would be to recognise wind as the service, rather than windfarms. Windfarms are also built on peat only because the location is suitable from an energy generation perspective, rather than because of inherent peatland properties. However, we decided to include windfarms since it is through these technologies that wind becomes a service, and the reality that the best location for windfarms often includes peatland areas, even if only by coincidence. There is also the potential that the perceived low value of peatland areas as opposed to, for example, agricultural areas, means that they are cheaper for windfarm use.

We have used participatory mapping for this exercise because we were concerned with delivery of services, rather than where is biophysically possible for services to be delivered (e.g., tourism relies on accessibility, and will not be delivered in places that are not accessible). Indeed, some of the services, such as tourism or recreation, are not easily mapped based only on biophysical characteristics. We have not, therefore, mapped the exact position of each service, but the general location, with some overlap on non-peat areas. While the maps therefore provide us with insight as to where conflict may arise and particular services need to be considered, management should map services at a much higher spatial resolution.

Thresholds for ecosystem services provision

When managing peatland for ecosystem service provision there are thresholds for some services whereby the service is so damaged it can no longer be managed for, or it has reached a level where further management is not required. Participants identified thresholds for fifteen of the services provided by peatlands (Table 5). However, they also noted significant spatial variation in where these were applicable, and therefore they may not apply in all areas.

Some similarities between ecosystem services thresholds can be identified. The siting of forestry plantations and wind farms on peatlands is often considered to be damaging to the nature of the peatland, particularly with regards to carbon, although this remains up for debate. However, although they lead to the reduction of carbon stored by peatland directly, when considering the total carbon budget for Scotland timber or wind farms may remain the most appropriate use of the land. The carbon benefit of removal of timber from an area must account for the additional carbon emitted if alternative timber is imported from elsewhere. Similarly, consideration the carbon savings from renewable energy produced by wind farms against the carbon emissions from extraction of peat and the drainage of peat for e.g. access and maintenance roads to erect wind turbines must be taken. Stakeholders identified that this full cycle of carbon accounting is necessary to properly address climate change and carbon emissions via peatland management.

Habitat provision was identified as relevant for the thresholds of four services: the provision of game, wildlife watching, wellbeing, and tourism. It is also likely that these services are interacting with one another, with wellbeing and tourism both benefited by wildlife watching and, to a lesser extent, game shooting. In these cases the thresholds for game provision will likely be lower than that for wildlife watching, which will require a more diverse habitat, but does provide the opportunity to link the services where they overlap. For wellbeing and tourism it is likely that additional non-peatland infrastructure, such as access roads, parking or accommodation would also be needed to access the service.

Finally, community and cultural connection was identified as important within thresholds relating to both food and peat extraction for fuel. It was noted that particular attention needed to be taken of the cultural connection of these activities, that thresholds for either food provision or peat cutting should only be set by those communities that rely on peatlands to meet food or energy needs.

Table 5 Thresholds under which management of peatland for this ecosystem services would not be possible (minimum service provision) or over which management would not be necessary as this service is being fully provided (maximum service provision). Note that these thresholds are highly spatially variable as well as context specific and therefore may not be relevant for all peatland management. Thresholds may also not account for all aspects of a service.

Service	Minimum service provision	Maximum service provision
Food	The minimum service needs to be linked to food security, including accounting for community food growing. A single limit for minimum service provision would therefore not be relevant.	The maximum sustainable level of livestock is estimated at 0.02 livestock units per hectare. No maximum was identified for other food types.
Game hunting	Habitat needs to be provided for game species.	No maximum identified.
Financial returns	Project needs to predict a positive cost benefit ratio.	No maximum identified

Carbon storage and sequestration	No minimum identified.	Success would be achieved when the site becomes a sink. This would include both above and belowground carbon where forest to bog conversion is considered. Forest to bog conversion should also include the carbon produced through the importation of replacement timber.
Flooding	No minimum identified.	Reduced or delayed flood peaks.
Energy - peat cutting	No minimum identified.	Cultural association as well as fuel poverty means that some cutting should be permitted but this should be as low as possible. Any reductions must include alternative fuel provision.
Energy - wind farms	Should only be possible where total (life cycle) carbon benefits, including that saved by the use of renewable energy, are positive.	No maximum identified.
Wildlife watching	Area must contain iconic species and associated attractive habitat.	No maximum identified.
Timber	The carbon benefits of continuing timber production should exceed the benefits of forest to bog conversion. This should include the carbon cost of importing alternative timber.	No maximum identified.
Regulating water scarcity	No minimum identified.	Stable water table.
Surface cooling	No minimum identified.	Complete sphagnum/vegetation cover.
Educational services	Peat needs to be available and accessible.	No maximum identified.
Well-being	Needs to contain species and habitat to make it attractive, and be accessible.	No maximum identified.
Tourism	Need to contain species and habitat to make it attractive, and be accessible.	No maximum identified.
Recreation	Need to be accessible and in good condition	No maximum identified.

Bundles of ecosystem services

The use of conceptual maps provided a visual tool to understand existing relationships between ecosystem services. Figure 2 outlines the ecosystem services with the largest number of connections, both positive and negative, as combined from the four original maps, seen in Appendix 2. Energy and carbon storage had the widest range of connections with twenty-eight connections respectively. Energy generated the largest amount of outward negative connections at twenty-two, in part due to a group in workshop two that selected energy to have a negative impact on all other services related to peat. Both timber and whisky followed this trend with nine of eleven and twelve of fifteen connections respectively being outwardly negative. Biodiversity and recreation both had a significantly larger number of positive connections to other services, at thirteen and eleven respectively. Carbon storage, flood prevention/mitigation, game, cultural heritage, and biodiversity credits all held a similar ratio of positive to negative connections, suggesting a more complex and interconnected picture of these ecosystem services.

As a result of having two workshops some opposing or duplicate services were suggested; workshop one used the term “flood prevention/ mitigation,” whilst workshop two simply used “flooding,” ultimately the former was taken forward and the use of flooding was adjusted within the final matrix. Recreation was condensed from a selection of similar terms; biodiversity recreation, commercial recreation and communal recreation. Similarly, water quality was combined with drinking water quality to form a more comprehensive understanding.

Figure 2 Final conceptual map of peatland ecosystem services. Blue arrows represent positive links, while orange arrows represent negative links. Energy had negative links to all other services, and so has been represented by bold arrows.

Through the conceptual maps three distinct bundles of services became apparent. These are services that have positive connections, and so management to increase one service is likely to result in an increase in the other (Figure 3):

Carbon centred – This bundle was dominated by the service of carbon storage, and included services predominantly related to biodiversity and water. Tourism and recreation specifically linked to biodiversity are also included in this bundle, based on the assumption that these include passive use, such as observation from a viewing platform or bird hide, as opposed to active use, such as hillwalking.

Non-extractive use – Dominated by links to flood prevention and mitigation, this bundle includes water quality and storage services, where it overlaps with the carbon centred bundle, but also includes non-extractive active use, such as recreation, food production and game shooting, which is in opposition with the carbon centred bundle.

Traditional use – The traditional use bundle included extractive uses, such as extraction of peat for use as fuel, shooting of game, and whisky production. Additionally, it also included links to cultural heritage and tourism.

Figure 3 Bundles of ecosystem services.

Although these three bundles are not exclusive of each other, they represent three distinct use types, where some services are in opposition to the other use types. Ten of the services considered by the pool of workshop participants do not appear in any of the bundles, these are: jobs in rural areas, growing media, surface cooling, disease control, healthy fisheries, building, windfarms, illegal waste, and military training grounds. This is because these services were not well linked within the

conceptual maps, having between ten (jobs in rural areas) and zero (military training grounds) links to other concepts. The lack of links to jobs in rural areas was identified as significant, particularly given the benefits of timber production, an alternative use of peat in this area. Understanding the needs of management of peat for carbon in particular would be beneficial, so that training could be targeted to local communities, and jobs in rural areas more readily realised as a benefit of peatland management in line with government priorities.

Some of the less connected services were not considered by our workshop participants as truly “services” provided by peat. For buildings, illegal waste dumping and windfarms; peat simply exists in the same location as these uses, rather than being a critical part of the service, and so was seen as less connected. Surface cooling, disease control, healthy fisheries, and military training grounds were considered more niche and less known services of peatlands by the pool of workshop participants, and only included in a subset of maps. While this does not mean that they are not important or connected services where they occur, they are likely limited in scope, or not yet well understood. Growing media extraction is widely considered to be damaging to peatlands, and so has limited links to other services. It is also expected to cease in the near future due to incoming legislation, and so was perceived as of little importance in future management.

Prioritise valuation gaps

The highest priority for research was identified by the workshop participants as the valuation of peatland for water quality (Table 6). The main focus was on drinking water quality, including benefits to Scottish Water for the life expectancy of their water monitoring sensors as well as the direct benefits of reduced water cleaning. Water quality was also identified as underpinning many other services, including those for biodiversity, and as a potential measure of landscape restoration success, with management in the Flow Country given as a particular example.

Flooding, energy, timber, and carbon storage were also identified as important gaps (Table 6). Flood prevention stakeholders identified existing research on forestry impacts on flooding as a potential framework for valuation. It was recognised that for flooding the largest challenge is likely to be that the biophysical data is not yet accurate enough to reliably predict peatland impacts on flooding. However, climate change means that flooding is likely to be of higher importance in coming years and developing the economic data alongside the biophysical will be beneficial.

Energy included all energy production from peatlands, including as a site for wind farms. Considerations here centred around energy security and the connections to cultural practise with regards to peat cutting. The potential total carbon budget benefits of windfarms vs traditional energy generation was highlighted as of importance.

The total carbon budget was also highlighted in timber production. Stakeholders were particularly interested to understand the impact of not planting on marginal peatlands on the carbon expended on importing timber that would no longer be produced domestically.

Carbon storage was identified as important due to the significant role that peatland management plays within Scotland’s climate change plan. Although carbon storage has the best documented valuation of all services considered; improvements to understandings of the valuation were thought to be useful.

All of the services identified as of high importance for future research are also services identified as already having high strength of evidence for their provision. This suggests that although the provision of the services and their value are well known, the details of the service still need to be understood. That is, there is not a lack of evidence, but lack of understanding how this can be applied to management of peatlands, and how trade-offs and differing timescales are managed.

Although not identified as high importance via the voting system, stakeholders also identified wellbeing as being an important service provided by peatlands, primarily due to the lack of current knowledge on how peatland landscapes may contribute to wellbeing. Due to public consultations often identifying jobs provided by forestry as important for continuing forestry on peatland, the value of jobs provided by peatlands management were also identified as a potential area for future research. Food provision was mentioned in workshops and the sole interview carried out, particularly given that peatlands were identified as often being perceived as wastelands and the production of food can provide them with a conceptual value for the wider population. Finally, roles in fire mitigation were identified as highly topical as peatland management could be used for mitigating fire spread.

Table 6 prioritisation of research into valuation of ecosystem services provided by peatlands by workshop participants

Priority	Service	Number of votes
Highest priority	Water quality (inc. drinking water)	9
High priority	Flooding	4
	Energy	3
	Timber	3
	Carbon storage	3
Medium priority	Regulation of water scarcity	2
	Financial services	2
	Air quality	2
	Flood prevention	2
	Well-being	2
Lower priority	Mitigation of fire risk	1
	Recreational environment of biodiversity	1
	Wildlife watching	1
	Educational services	1
	Disease control	1
	Growing media	1
	Healthy fisheries	1
	Jobs in rural area	1
	Food	1

Conclusions and next steps

Building on the evidence review carried out in 2023 (Roberts et al., 2023) these workshops identified:

- Twenty-two additional ecosystem services produced by peatland not present in the existing published literature.
- Areas of high demand for peatland services in the Borders, Central Belt, and Cairngorms National Park.
- Limited and variable evidence for thresholds for the management of peatland for ecosystem services.
- Three bundles of services produced by peatland as carbon storage, non-extractive use, and traditional use.
- Finally, research gaps in the valuation of water quality, flooding, energy, timber, and carbon.

This work forms part of the CentrePeat project, within the Scottish Government Strategic Research Program. The results will feed into developing a toolkit for valuing the most important peatland ecosystem services. Using choice experiments we will investigate the trade-offs between competing services, and potential options for mitigating this competition. The toolkit will later be applied to case studies.

References

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Appendix 1 – Conflicts in conceptual map

Appendix table 1 – Record of decisions made on directions of links in combined conceptual map where opposing links were present.

From	To	Conclusion
Timber	Carbon storage	-1 Although discussions were had regarding the need to consider the full life cycle of timber production and the impact of importing timber on total carbon storage, which may result in continued timber production being beneficial to total carbon budgets, for the current research we have retained the conventional negative link between timber and carbon storage.
Energy	Cultural Heritage	1 Cutting of peat for fuel is long established traditional practise. Although it may be in opposition to current values of some, it remains linked to cultural values.
Flooding	Water Quality	-1 Increased flooding is well established to reduce water quality.
Water Quality	Flooding	0 The direction of this link was ambiguous in the map production, and so was removed, assumed to be in the direction of flooding to water quality.

Appendix 2

Appendix 2 – Conceptual mapping from workshop 1

Appendix 2 – Conceptual mapping from workshop 2

